

Sensitivity Analysis of Ultrasonic Plate Sonotrode: Influence of Measurement Accuracy and Manufacturing Tolerances

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Abstract. Ultrasonic excitation offers significant potential to enhance manufacturing processes by temporarily reducing fiber-fiber friction during critical steps, such as needle punching in nonwoven textile production. This effect can be achieved through the integration of a specially designed plate sonotrode. To evaluate its vibration properties, a prototype and dedicated test bench were developed based on a generic optimization process. In this study, the sensitivity of the ultrasonic plate sonotrode was investigated with respect to measurement accuracy, which can be affected by the positional precision of the gantry system or the resolution of the vibrometer. Acceptable uncertainties in the experimental setup were identified and quantified. Furthermore, the influence of manufacturing tolerances on deviations from the target mode shape and the desired natural frequency was assessed. The results show that plate thickness has a pronounced impact on vibration behavior, while the proposed validation approach confirms that accurate characterization of mode shapes and resonance frequencies is achievable under realistic experimental conditions.

Keywords: Ultrasonic, Plate Sonotrode, Tolerances, Sensitivity.

1 Introduction

Ultrasonic assistance offers a promising way to improve the efficiency and robustness of nonwoven production, where high friction and dynamic fiber interactions pose significant challenges. The use of ultrasonic excitation in manufacturing has gained attention due to its ability to modify contact conditions, enhance process efficiency, and influence material behavior. Reported applications include acoustic levitation [1,2], friction reduction at sliding interfaces [3,4] as well as the reduction of process loads accompanied by improved productivity [5-7]. A field with promising yet underexplored potential for ultrasonic assistance is the production of nonwoven textiles. During processing, the fiber is subjected to mechanical interaction. In the needle punching process, randomly oriented fibers are mechanically entangled by repeated penetration with barbed needles, as illustrated in Fig. 1a. Introducing high-frequency oscillations into the fiber assembly using a vibrating plate sonotrode can temporarily reduce fiber-fiber friction during this critical step [4]. This reduction can lower the risk of fiber damage and decrease wear on cost-intensive needles.

To investigate this concept, an optimized plate sonotrode design was presented in [8], using a genetic optimization strategy that identifies plate parameters that offer a uniform operational mode shape, see Fig. 1b, at the targeted natural frequency close to 20 kHz. A dedicated experimental setup was developed to validate the simulated design. The prototype stripper plate can be characterized using a laser vibrometer mounted on a gantry system, enabling spatially resolved measurement of out-of-plane vibration amplitudes, see Fig. 1c. To ensure sufficient measurement accuracy, the vibration at each measurement point can be recorded with a sampling rate of 192 kHz. The acquired data is digitized and further processed using a Quantum MX410B data acquisition module. For further characterization of the vibration properties, a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of the laser vibrometer signal will be performed.

Fig.1 Abstract representation of the needle punching process for nonwoven production, showing the perforated plate, the targeted mode shape, and the test bench setup used for prototype characterization.

2 Methodology and Results

In developing the test bench and prototype, several parameters influencing the reliability of the validation procedure were investigated. The objective was to reproduce the vibration behavior predicted in the simulation and to quantify the accuracy of the measurement process. The prototype quality is assessed based on the deviation of the measured resonance frequency

from the targeted natural frequency and the Modal Assurance Criterion (MAC) [9]. The MAC compares the experimentally measured mode shape with the finite element analysis (FEA) mode shape. To enable this comparison, the nodal displacement field of the FEA model is interpolated onto the set of measured points.

This study examines the influence of the following two factors on the accuracy of the prototype characterization and the validation workflow: Accuracy of the measurement system and manufacturing tolerances of the plate sonotrode. Each measurement dataset consists of measurement points $i \in I$ defined by spatial coordinates and out-of-plane displacement amplitude $(x_i, y_i, U_{z,i})_{i \in I}$. Measurement uncertainties therefore arise either from the positional accuracy of the gantry system or the resolution of the vibrometer. To assess these effects, synthetic measurement data were generated from a simulated plate and perturbed with normally distributed noise \mathcal{N} . Assuming the absence of systematic errors, the perturbations follow zero-mean normal distributions:

$$U_z^{\text{noisy}} = U_z + \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{U_z}^2), \quad x^{\text{noisy}} = x + \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_x^2), \quad y^{\text{noisy}} = y + \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_y^2).$$

For each noisy dataset, the MAC value with respect to the reference measurement was computed. Evaluating the influence of artificial noise, the MAC value decreases with increasing standard deviation σ . The analysis shows that for a noise level of σ_{U_z} corresponding to $1.25 \mu\text{m}$, a MAC value of 0.985 can still be obtained. Since the vibrometer used in the test bench provides a resolution of $0.5 \mu\text{m}$, no significant deterioration of the validation accuracy is anticipated. A decrease of the MAC to approximately 0.985 due to positional uncertainty occurs for deviations on the order of $\sigma_x = \sigma_y = 1 \text{ mm}$. The gantry positioning accuracy 0.1 mm is therefore more than sufficient.

To analyze the influence of manufacturing tolerances, variations in plate length (775.23 mm), width (271.55 mm), thickness (14.98 mm), and corner radius (4.9 mm) were simulated with different tolerance levels. For each level, the resulting mode shape for an excitation frequency equal to the original natural frequency was evaluated. This was done by comparing each simulation result with the simulation without geometric deviations using the MAC. The results indicate that plate thickness has a pronounced effect on the vibration behavior, see Tab. 1. In contrast, the remaining geometric parameters show no significant influence on the mode shape for tolerance levels within $\pm 0.5 \text{ mm}$, resulting in MAC values of 0.99 or higher.

Table 1. MAC values for tolerance variations in stripper plate thickness.

Tolerances	$\pm 0.5 \text{ mm}$	$\pm 0.3 \text{ mm}$	$\pm 0.1 \text{ mm}$	$\pm 0.05 \text{ mm}$	$\pm 0.03 \text{ mm}$	$\pm 0.01 \text{ mm}$
MAC values for thickness	0.443	0.444	0.712	0.825	0.993	0.999

3 Conclusion

Overall, the study shows that measurement uncertainties within the capabilities of the test bench have only minor influence on the measurement of the plate vibration. Manufacturing tolerances, especially plate thickness, significantly affect the vibration behavior and must be tightly controlled for reliable prototype validation.

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References

1. Distel, F.M. and Reinhart, G.: Automated design and optimization of rectangular plate sonotrodes for squeeze film levitation. *Journal of Vibration Engineering and Technologies* 3(2): 151–160 (2015).
2. Cao, Y., Zhu, Y., Nan, Li. H., Wang, C., Su, H., Yin, Z., and Ding, W.: Development and performance of a novel ultrasonic vibration plate sonotrode for grinding. *Journal of Manufacturing Processes* 57: 174–186. DOI:10.1016/j.jmapro.2020.06.030 (2020).
3. Littmann, W.: Piezoelektrische, resonant betriebene Ultraschall-Leistungswandler mit nichtlinearen mechanischen Randbedingungen: Zugl.: Paderborn, Univ., Diss., 2003, HNI-Verlagsschriftenreihe, volume 124. Paderborn: Heinz-Nixdorf-Inst. ISBN 978-3-935433-33-4.7 (2003).
4. Archut, J.L., Kins, R., Heider, Y., Cloppenburg, F., Markert, B., Gries, T., and Corves, B.: A study of the mechanical response of nonwovens excited by plate vibration. *Applied Mechanics* 3(2): 496–516. DOI:10.3390/applmech3020029 (2022).
5. Kumar, S., Wu, C.S., Padhy, G.K., and Ding, W.: Application of ultrasonic vibrations in welding and metal processing: A status review. *Journal of Manufacturing Processes* 26: 295–322. DOI:10.1016/j.jmapro.2017.02.027 (2017).
6. Lais, H., Lowe, P.S., Wrobel, L.C., and Gan, T.H.: Investigation of ultrasonic sonotrode design to improve the performance of ultrasonic fouling removal. *IEEE Access* 7: 148897–148912. DOI:10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2946702 (2019).
7. Peng, Z., Han, A., Wang, C., Jin, H. and Zhang, X.: Ultrasonic vibration cutting of advanced aerospace materials: a critical review of in-service functional performance. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing and Special Equipment* 5(1): 137–169. DOI:10.1108/JIMSE-12-2023-0016 (2024).
8. Bolk, J., Mirz, C., Kirk, E., Corves, B.: Mode Shape Optimisation of a Plate in the Ultrasonic Frequency Range. In: 11. IFToMM D-A-CH Konferenz 2025: 20./21. Februar 2025, FH Kärnten, Villach. DOI:10.17185/dupublico/82897 (2025).
9. Allemang, R.-J.: The modal assurance criterion – twenty years of use and abuse. *Sound and Vibration* (37): 14–23 (2003).